

On the Direct Product of Cubic Neutrosophic Subrings

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Abstract: This paper introduces the direct product of two cubic neutrosophic sets and examines its fundamental properties. A formal definition of the construction is presented, and its behavior is studied through a series of results. The investigation includes closure properties, internal relationships within the product, and preservation of essential features in the combined setting. Several theorems are established to characterize the operation of the direct product, together with conditions ensuring its consistency. The study emphasizes the role of direct products in broadening the scope of cubic neutrosophic sets and provides a systematic treatment within this framework.

Keywords: Cubic Neutrosophic Sets, Cubic Neutrosophic Subrings, Cubic Neutrosophic Normal Subrings, Cubic Neutrosophic ideals, Direct Product.

1. Introduction

The theory of fuzzy sets (shortly, FS) was first introduced by Zadeh [12] in 1965. This concept enabled the representation of uncertainty in mathematical terms by assigning each element of a set a membership value between 0 and 1. In 1975, Zadeh [13] further extended this idea by presenting the interval-valued fuzzy set (shortly, IVFS), in which each element is associated with an interval of membership values rather than a single value.

In 1984, Abu Osman [6] contributed to this line of research by developing the concept of the direct product of fuzzy subgroups. Later, in 2005, Smarandache [10] established the neutrosophic set (shortly, NS), a significant generalization of FS that incorporated three independent functions. In the same year, Wang et al. 2005 [11] introduced interval-valued neutrosophic sets (shortly, IVNS), which integrated the concept of interval values into the neutrosophic framework. These advancements opened new pathways for exploring algebraic structures under fuzzy and neutrosophic environments.

Subsequently, Jun et al. [9] in 2012 proposed the notion of cubic sets (shortly, CS), which combined the features of both FS and IVFS. Continuing this line of research, Chinnadurai et al. [3] in 2016 investigated certain concepts related to the direct product of cubic ideals in Γ -near rings, thereby extending the scope of cubic set theory within ring-theoretic structures. In 2019, Kausar et al. [7] studied the direct product of finite intuitionistic anti-fuzzy normal subrings over non-associative rings, further enriching the field.

More recent works include Gulsar et al. [5] in 2021, he examined the direct product of complex intuitionistic fuzzy subrings and established results that extended this concept within the intuitionistic fuzzy framework. Similarly, Anitha et al. [1,2] in 2022 and 2024 explored the direct product of neutrosophic Q-fuzzy subrings and subsequently introduced norms into neutrosophic multi-fuzzy subrings. Their findings highlighted how different norms influence the behavior of fuzzy and neutrosophic subrings, thereby deepening the understanding of the interaction between fuzzy logic, neutrosophic sets, and algebraic systems.

The direct product of cubic neutrosophic sets provides a unified framework to study algebraic substructures such as subrings, ideals, and normal subrings under uncertainty. It combines the flexibility of cubic sets with the richness of neutrosophic logic.

2. Preliminary

Definition 2.1 [8] Let \mathcal{X} be a set that is not empty. A CS \mathcal{C} in \mathcal{X} is a structure defined as

$\mathcal{C} = \{ \check{n}, \bar{\zeta}_{\mathcal{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathcal{C}}(\check{n})/\check{n} \in X \}$ and $\mathcal{C} = \langle \bar{\zeta}_{\mathcal{C}}, \zeta_{\mathcal{C}} \rangle$, where $\bar{\zeta}_{\mathcal{C}} = [\zeta^L, \zeta^U]$ represents an IVFS in \mathcal{X} , and $\zeta_{\mathcal{C}}$ is a FS in \mathcal{X} .

Definition 2.2[9] Consider \mathcal{X} as a universal set. A NS on \mathcal{X} is expressed as $\mathcal{N} = \{ \check{n}, \zeta_{\mathcal{N}}(\check{n}), \varrho_{\mathcal{N}}(\check{n}), \varsigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\check{n})/\check{n} \in X \}$ where $\zeta, \varrho, \varsigma \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.3 [4] An IVNS of \mathcal{X} is defined as $\bar{\mathcal{N}} = \{ \check{n}, \bar{\zeta}_{\bar{\mathcal{N}}}(\check{n}), \bar{\varrho}_{\bar{\mathcal{N}}}(\check{n}), \bar{\varsigma}_{\bar{\mathcal{N}}}(\check{n})/\check{n} \in X \}$ where $\bar{\zeta}, \bar{\varrho}, \bar{\varsigma} \in [0,1]$.

3. Direct product on cubic Neutrosophic Subrings

Definition 3.1 Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty set. A cubic neutrosophic set (shortly, CNS) in \mathcal{X} . It can be expressed as $\mathfrak{C} = \{ \check{n}, \zeta^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})/\check{n} \in \mathcal{X} \}$.

Where $\zeta^*_{\mathfrak{C}} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}, \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}} \rangle \in [0,1]$, $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a i-v truth membership function and $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a truth membership function.

$\varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C}} = \langle \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}, \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}} \rangle \in [0,1]$, $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a i-v indeterminacy membership function and $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is an indeterminacy membership function.

$\varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C}} = \langle \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}, \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}} \rangle \in [0,1]$, $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a i-v falsity membership function and $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a falsity membership function.

With the condition that $0 \leq \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}} + \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}} + \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}} \leq 3$ and $0 \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}} + \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}} + \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}} \leq 3$.

Definition 3.2 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. Then the direct product of a cubic neutrosophic subring (shortly, CNSR) $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$, if it satisfies the following axioms, $\forall (\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

- (i) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$
- $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$
- $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max \{ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$
- $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{ \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$
- $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max \{ \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$
- $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{ \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(ii)} \quad & \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.3 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. Then $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Proof: Let $(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i)} \quad & \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1 - \check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1 - \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & = \min \{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1 - \check{n}_2), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1 - \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \geq \min \{\min\{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2)\}, \min\{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\}\} \\
 & = \min \{\min\{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1)\}, \min \{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\}\} \\
 & = \min \{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1 - \check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1 - \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & = \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1 - \check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1 - \check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \leq \max \{ \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2)\}, \max \{\zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\}\} \\
 & = \max \{ \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1)\}, \max \{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\}\} \\
 & = \max \{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \quad \text{and} \\
 & \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}; \\
 & \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \quad \text{and} \\
 & \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(ii)} \quad & \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\
 & = \min \{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\
 & \geq \min \{\min\{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2)\}, \min\{\check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1), \check{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min \{ \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1) \}, \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2) \} \} \\
 &= \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \} \\
 \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2)\} \\
 &= \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2)\} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2)\}, \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2) \} \} \\
 &= \max \{ \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1)\}, \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2) \} \} \\
 &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &\leq \max\{\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \text{ and} \\
 \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &\geq \min \{ \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}; \\
 \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &\leq \max\{\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \text{ and} \\
 \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &\geq \min \{ \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Corollary 3.4 Let $\mathfrak{C}_1, \mathfrak{C}_2, \mathfrak{C}_3, \dots, \mathfrak{C}_n$ be CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{R}_3, \dots, \mathfrak{R}_n$ correspondingly. Then $\mathfrak{C}_1 \times \mathfrak{C}_2 \times \mathfrak{C}_3 \times \dots \times \mathfrak{C}_n$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2 \times \mathfrak{R}_3 \times \dots \times \mathfrak{R}_n$.

Remark 3.5 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly and $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ be CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. Then both \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} are need not be CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Theorem 3.6 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &\geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}) \\
 \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &\leq \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}) \\
 \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &\leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}), \forall \check{n}, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $\check{n}, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n} - \check{n}), (\check{k} - \check{k})\} \\
 &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, \check{k}) - (\check{n}, \check{k})\} \\
 &\geq \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}) \} \\
 &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') = \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n} - \check{n}), (\check{k} - \check{k})\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, \check{k}) - (\check{n}, \check{k})\} \\
 &\leq \max \{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k})\} \\
 &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &\leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}) \text{ and} \\
 \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') &\leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Theorem 3.7 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then atleast one of the following statement must hold.

- (i) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
- (ii) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$.

Proof: Let $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ be a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. By contradiction suppose that none of the statements hold. Then there exist $\check{n} \in \mathfrak{R}_1$ and $\check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_2$ such that

- (i) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') < \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') > \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') > \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') < \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') > \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') < \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
- (ii) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) < \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) > \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) > \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) < \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) > \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) < \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Thus } \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}, \check{k}) &= \min \{\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})\} \\
 &> \min \{\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0')\} \\
 &= \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(0, 0').
 \end{aligned}$$

Which is contradiction. Thus either

- (i) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') &\leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}) \\ \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') &\leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}) \\ \text{(ii) } \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}) \\ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}) \\ \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}). \text{ Hold, } \forall \check{n} \in \mathfrak{R}_1, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_2. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.8 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then either \mathfrak{C} is a CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 (or) \mathfrak{D} is a CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Proof: Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then one of the following two statements hold.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') &\geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}) \\ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') &\leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}) \\ \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') &\leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}) \\ \text{(ii) } \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}) \\ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}) \\ \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) &\leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}), \forall \check{n} \in \mathfrak{R}_1, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_2. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose condition (i) hold. Let $\check{n}, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i) } \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) &= \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0' - 0') \} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}} \{ (\check{n} - \check{k}), (0' - 0') \} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}} \{ (\check{n}, 0') - (\check{k}, 0') \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \}, \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \} \\ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0' - 0') \} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}} \{ (\check{n} - \check{k}), (0' - 0') \} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}} \{ (\check{n}, 0') - (\check{k}, 0') \} \\ &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \}, \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \} \} \\ &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}; \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) \geq \min \{ \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \} \text{ and}$$

$$\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) \leq \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}; \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n} - \check{k}) \geq \min \{ \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(ii) } \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) &= \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \} \\ &= \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, 0')(\check{k}, 0')\} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \}, \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0')\} \} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, 0')(\check{k}, 0')\} \\ &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \}, \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \} \} \\ &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}; \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \min \{ \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \} \text{ and}$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}; \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \min \{ \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \}.$$

Hence \mathfrak{C} is a CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 . In the similar way we can prove that \mathfrak{D} is a CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Example 3.9 Consider the ring Z_2 and Z_4 . Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNSR defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}(\check{n}) &= \begin{cases} \langle [0.7,0.8]0.4, [0.6,0.7]0.8, [0.4,0.7]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } \check{n} = 0 \\ \langle [0.3,0.4]0.7, [0.5,0.8]0.3, [0.7,0.8]0.6 \rangle & \text{if } \check{n} = 1 \end{cases} \\ \mathfrak{D}(\check{k}) &= \begin{cases} \langle [0.6,0.7]0.2, [0.2,0.4]0.7, [0.1,0.3]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } \check{k} = 0 \\ \langle [0.5,0.6]0.4, [0.4,0.6]0.5, [0.2,0.4]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } \check{k} = 2 \\ \langle [0.3,0.5]0.8, [0.7,0.8]0.1, [0.4,0.5]0.2 \rangle & \text{if } \check{k} = 1,3 \end{cases} \\ \mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}(\check{n}, \check{k}) &= \begin{cases} \langle [0.6,0.7]0.4, [0.6,0.7]0.7, [0.4,0.7]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } (0,0) \\ \langle [0.3,0.5]0.8, [0.7,0.8]0.1, [0.4,0.7]0.2 \rangle & \text{if } (0,1), (0,3) \\ \langle [0.5,0.6]0.4, [0.6,0.7]0.5, [0.4,0.7]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } (0,2) \\ \langle [0.3,0.4]0.7, [0.5,0.8]0.3, [0.7,0.8]0.5 \rangle & \text{if } (1,0), (1,2) \\ \langle [0.3,0.4]0.8, [0.7,0.8]0.1, [0.7,0.8]0.2 \rangle & \text{if } (1,1), (1,3) \end{cases} . \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(1,0) - (1,0)\} \not\leq \max \{ [0.5,0.8], [0.5,0.8] \}$. Therefore converse of the above theorem is not true.

Definition 4.3 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. Then the direct product of $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a cubic neutrosophic ideal (shortly, CNI) of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. If it satisfies the following axioms, $\forall (\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

- (i) $\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \max\{\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \min \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
- (ii) $\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \max \{\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \min\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \min\{\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \max \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \min\{\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \max \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}.$

Theorem 4.4 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNLI(RI) of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly, then $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ be a CNLI(RI) of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Proof: Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNLI(RI) of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly.

Let $(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

By theorem 3.3 $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Now, it is enough to show the following

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\ &= \min \{\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\ &\geq \min \{\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\} \\ &\geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\ &= \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1\check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1\check{k}_2)\} \\ &\leq \max \{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2).$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \text{ and}$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2).$$

Hence $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is CNLI of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

In the same way we can prove $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNRI of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Theorem 4.5 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNI of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly, then $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ be a CNI of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Proof: Result follows the above theorem.

Theorem 4.6 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNSs of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNLI(RI) of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then either \mathfrak{C} is a CNLI(RI) of \mathfrak{R}_1 (or) \mathfrak{D} is a CNLI(RI) of \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Proof: Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNSs of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly and $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNLI of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. By theorem 3.8 with

$$\tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$$

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}). \text{ Hence } \mathfrak{C} \text{ is a CNSR of } \mathfrak{R}_1.$$

It is enough to show the following

$$\tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$$

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}), \forall \check{n}, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2.$$

$$\tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) = \min \{ \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}), \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \}$$

$$= \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\}$$

$$= \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}, 0')$$

$$= \tilde{z}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k})$$

$$\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) = \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \}$$

$$= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\}$$

$$= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, 0')(\check{k}, 0')\}$$

$$= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}).$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}) \text{ and}$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}). \text{ Hence } \mathfrak{C} \text{ is a CNLI of } \mathfrak{R}_1.$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \geq \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$$

$$\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \leq \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$$

$$\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \leq \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}). \text{ We can show that } \mathfrak{D} \text{ is a CNLI of } \mathfrak{R}_2.$$

In the same way, we can prove that CNRI.

Theorem 4.7 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be two CNSs of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNI of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then either \mathfrak{C} is a CNI of \mathfrak{R}_1 (or) \mathfrak{D} is a CNI of \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Proof: Result follows the above theorem.

5. Direct Product on Cubic Neutrosophic Normal Subrings

Definition 5.1 A CNS $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ is said to be Cubic Neutrosophic Normal Subrings

(shortly, CNNSR), if it satisfies the following axioms, $\forall (\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2) \in \mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

- (i) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min \{\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max\{\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max\{\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1) - (\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
- (ii) $\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max \{\tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min\{\tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max \{\varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varrho_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \min\{\tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \tilde{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}$
 $\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \max \{\varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1), \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\}.$

Theorem 5.2 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$ then the following statements are true.

- (i) $\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
 $\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(0') \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n})$
- (ii) $\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$
 $\check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \check{\varrho}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varrho_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varrho_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k})$
 $\check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \leq \check{\varsigma}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}); \varsigma_{\mathfrak{C}}(0) \geq \varsigma_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}), \forall \check{n} \in \mathfrak{R}_1, \check{k} \in \mathfrak{R}_2.$

Proof: By theorem 3.8 \mathfrak{C} (or) \mathfrak{D} is a CNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 . The following is enough for normality.

If the condition (i) hold. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) &= \min \{ \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, 0'), (\check{k}, 0')\} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{k}, 0'), (\check{n}, 0')\} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{k}\check{n}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \min\{\check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n}), \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0')\} \\ &= \check{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n}) \\ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}\check{k}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}, 0')(\check{k}, 0')\} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{k}, 0')(\check{n}, 0')\} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{k}\check{n}), (0'0')\} \\ &= \max \{ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n}), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(0'0') \} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n}). \end{aligned}$$

Similarity,

$\varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) = \varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n})$ and $\varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}\check{k}) = \varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{k}\check{n})$. Hence \mathfrak{C} is a CNNSR of \mathfrak{R}_1 . In the same way (ii)

we can find \mathfrak{D} is a CNNSR of \mathfrak{R}_2 .

Theorem 5.3 Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. If $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

Proof: Let \mathfrak{C} and \mathfrak{D} be CNS of \mathfrak{R}_1 and \mathfrak{R}_2 correspondingly. By theorem 3.3 $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$. It is enough to show the normality.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &= \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2)\} \\ &= \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2 \check{n}_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2 \check{k}_1) \} \\ &= \tilde{\zeta}_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_2 \check{k}_2), (\check{n}_1 \check{k}_1)\} \\ \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), (\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2)\} \\ &= \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_1 \check{n}_2), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_1 \check{k}_2)\} \\ &= \max\{\zeta_{\mathfrak{C}}(\check{n}_2 \check{n}_1), \zeta_{\mathfrak{D}}(\check{k}_2 \check{k}_1)\} \\ &= \zeta_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_2 \check{k}_2), (\check{n}_1 \check{k}_1)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \varrho^*_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_2 \check{k}_2), (\check{n}_1 \check{k}_1)\}$ and

$\varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_1, \check{k}_1)(\check{n}_2, \check{k}_2)\} = \varsigma^*_{\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}}\{(\check{n}_2 \check{k}_2), (\check{n}_1 \check{k}_1)\}$. Hence $\mathfrak{C} \times \mathfrak{D}$ is a CNNSR of $\mathfrak{R}_1 \times \mathfrak{R}_2$.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced and examined the concept of the direct product of cubic neutrosophic sets, together with their association with subrings, ideals, and normal subrings. The results presented here extend the scope of cubic neutrosophic structures and establish meaningful connections between neutrosophic logic and classical algebraic systems. This study contributes to the advancement of uncertainty-based algebra and provides a solid foundation for further theoretical development.

For future research, we plan to explore the notions of cubic neutrosophic prime ideals and cubic neutrosophic primary ideals. These extensions are expected to deepen the understanding of ideal theory in the neutrosophic framework and may also serve as useful tools for applications in decision-making, information processing, and other computational models that involve uncertainty.

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